

Russians (of Viriatino Village)

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Anj Droë, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Russian Orthodox, Christian Traditions, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Religious Group

Viriatino is a small village in the Tambov Oblast of what is now Russia. This entry focuses on Viriatino in the 1950s, at which time Russia was part of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR). Secularization of the primarily Russian Orthodox Christian population in Viriatino first began following the First Russian Revolution in 1905 and accelerated after the Russian Revolution in 1917, at which time the Church was officially separated from the State and religious education was banned (Benet, 1970:289). The church in Viriatino was closed in 1933, and by the 1950s, many of the traditional religious beliefs and practices had been abandoned. Aspects of religion that were retained through state-sponsored secularization mainly related to marriage or treatment of the dead. Certain important holidays were also celebrated, but with fewer and less strict religious practices than had been observed in the past (such as required prayers or fasting). Some practices were still observed, but had lost much of their religious significance, such as baptism or the keeping of icons (paintings of religious figures) in a corner of the house. Because Church and State were explicitly separate, this entry does not consider the religion and the society to be coterminous.

Date Range: 1940 CE - 1965 CE

Region: Viriatino Village ca. 1955

Region tags: Russia

Viriatino Village, Tambov Oblast, USSR ca. 1955

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=rf10-086>

– Source 1 Description: Benet, Sula. 1970. *The Village of Viriatino: An Ethnographic Study of a Russian Village from before the Revolution to the Present*. Garden City, N.Y.: Anchor Books.

– Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=rf10-088>

– Source 2 Description: Dunn, Stephen Porter, and Ethel Dunn. 1963. "The Great Russian Peasant: Culture Change or Cultural Development?" *Ethnology* Vol. 2 (no. 3): 320-38.

– Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=rf10-087>

– Source 3 Description: Dunn, Stephen Porter, and Ethel Dunn. 1988. *The Peasants of Central Russia*. Prospect Heights, Ill.: Waveland Press, Inc.

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=rf10-000>.

– Source 1 Description: Shimkin, Demitri B. (Demitri Boris), and Teferi Abate Adem. 2021. "Culture Summary: Russians." New Haven: Human Relations Area Files.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Cultural contact was largely non-religious or secular in nature: "After the revolution of 1905-7, a more anticlerical, antireligious mood prevailed among the peasant miners. . . . Because of their contact with the organized workers [associated with the revolution of 1905-1907] some of the miners came back to the village confirmed atheists" (Benet, 1970:130).

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– I don't know

Notes: "After the revolution of 1905-7, a more anticlerical, antireligious mood prevailed among the peasant miners. . . . Because of their contact with the organized workers [associated with the revolution of 1905-1907] some of the miners came back to the village confirmed atheists" (Benet, 1970:130).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), "Internal warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), "External warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: While baptism was common, the practice had lost religious significance: "Among those religious customs which continue in practice but lack true significance are those connected with the birth of

children. Almost all of the children are baptized" (Benet, 1970:274).

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– I don't know

Notes: Christianity is by definition an evangelical religion, but no ethnographic evidence indicates that the Russians in Viriatino proselytized and recruited new members to Orthodox Russian Christianity.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: "After the Revolution the Church was separated from the State and religious instruction was abolished" (Benet, 1970:289).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "There was much truth in the villagers' opinion that the miners were godless. Even now the old people understand that their alienation from village life was the result of their work in the Donbass. According to Diakov who worked in the mines for nine years, 'when we emerged from the mines we were as black as the devil, and who would think of God?' Because of their contact with the organized workers some of the miners came back to the village confirmed atheists." (Benet, 1970:130).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1500

Notes: "The population of the village [Viriatino] is difficult to determine from the information given in the text [Benet, 1970], and appears to vary widely from year to year, but is in the neighborhood of 1,500" (Dunn and Dunn, 1963:320).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: While ethnographic evidence indicates that priests were present, they were not described in detail for the time focus of this entry: "She [an informant] started work when she was an adolescent, working during the winter as a housemaid for the local priest [in Viriatino] and the teachers and during the summer hiring herself out as a day laborer" (Benet, 1970:278).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral

scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: "In all other instances [non-civil burials] a religious ritual is observed including a reading of scripture over the dead and those parts of the service which do not require the presence of a priest" (Benet, 1970:275). Additionally, The Russians of Viriatino held largely Christian beliefs and the Bible is the scripture of Christianity. Thus, it can be assumed that the Russians in Viriatino have scripture.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic indicates that a church was present, but had been closed: "In 1933 the village church was closed in accordance with the wishes of the bulk of the Viriatino population" (Benet, 1970:271). No evidence indicates the presence of monumental religious architecture.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: "One of the main reasons these icons [traditional paintings of religious figures] are still kept is because the people are afraid to defy convention" (Benet, 1970:271).

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

Notes: "In her [an informant's] own words she began to forget the holidays, and although there were icons [traditional paintings of religious figures] in the house nobody in the family prayed" (Benet, 1970:274).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that some belief in personhood continuing after death of the body was present: "... only the very oldest women continue to observe certain rites connected with a whole cycle of ancient notions about life after death" (Benet, 1970:275).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that some belief in personhood continuing after death of the body was present: "... only the very oldest women continue to observe certain rites connected with a whole cycle of ancient notions about life after death" (Benet, 1970:275).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "In the majority of families those religious customs connected with the burial of the dead are strictly maintained; burials are traditionally Christian" (Benet, 1970:275).

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of cremation. Rather, evidence indicates adherents were interred (see Benet, 1970:275).

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of mummification. Rather, evidence indicates adherents were interred (see Benet, 1970:275).

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "In the majority of families those religious customs connected with the burial of the dead are strictly maintained; burials are traditionally Christian" (Benet, 1970:275).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of cannibalism. Rather, evidence indicates adherents were interred (see Benet, 1970:275).

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of exposure to elements. Rather, evidence indicates adherents were interred (see Benet, 1970:275).

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of feeding to animals. Rather, evidence indicates adherents were interred (see Benet, 1970:275).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of co-sacrifices.

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Notes: While ethnographic evidence does not indicate that grave goods were typically present, burial clothes can be important: "For the most part the deceased are buried in what they wore when alive, if possible in an all-white or dark suit" (Benet, 1970:238).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 238, High Gods, indicates that a high god was present (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, High Gods, a high god was "present, active, and specifically supportive of human morality" (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34). While present, the supreme high god is not described in substantial ethnographic detail.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The Russians of Viriatino held largely Christian beliefs and in the Christian faith, the supreme high god is considered to be a sky deity. Thus, it can be assumed that the supreme high god propitiated by the Russians in Viriatino was a sky deity.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See Benet, 1970:274 for a description of the traditional social norms that were still held at the time period this entry focuses on.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Moral pressure of the community as a whole also has a bearing; in frequent instances where there is no inner conviction as to the meaning of a particular custom it will be retained because the people are afraid of what their relatives, neighbors, and fellow villagers will say" (Benet, 1970:271).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that castration was previously present in the 19th century. However, no evidence indicates that the practice continued to the current time focus (Dunn and Dunn, 1988).

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: "Nobody, for example, fasts any more, but the 'breaking of the fast' is observed by beginning the Easter meal with eggs, milk, and cottage cheese, after which everyone sits down to the table" (Benet, 1970:273).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required permanent bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that sacrifice of time was no longer required by the time focus of this entry. See Benet, 1970:271 for details.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: "Specific ritual observance during the different holidays is almost entirely obliterated, but a few elements of religious significance are still preserved to a greater or lesser degree depending on the family" (Benet, 1970:273). See Benet, 1970:273 for more information on household rituals surrounding holidays. Furthermore, marriage rituals were also viewed as important and were privately held (Benet, 1970:268).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that large-scale rituals were previously present, but were no longer observed at the time this entry focuses on. See Benet, 1970:272-273 for details.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: "A godmother and godfather is chosen usually from among the younger generation" (Benet, 1970:274).

Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that godparents were chosen for every child baptized (Benet, 1970:274).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: At the time focus of this entry, Viriatino was a part of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics

(USSR), which was a state society. According to SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy beyond Local Community, the Russians of Viriatino had four levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a large state or empire (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 32).

Welfare

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "Elderly people who have worked on the collective farm . . . and also invalids . . . shall . . . be entitled to a personal pension equal to what they would receive for working twenty-five to fifty percent of the average annual number of days worked by them during the last twenty-five years of their active participation" (Benet, 1970:198).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: "After the Revolution the Church was separated from the State and religious instruction was abolished. . . In Viriatino there were villagers opposed to antireligious education, and some of them did not allow their children to attend school at all" (Benet, 1970:289).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The effects in adult education together with the tremendous progress of the Soviet schools for children hastened the formation of an atheistic outlook among the village youth, but this process still did not affect the older generation which was in the main responsible for preservation of traditional forms" (Benet, 1970:271).

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: "With very few exceptions, modern young men and women in the country receive a minimum of seven years of education" (Benet, 1970:249).

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: "The village soviet forms the nucleus of all social life in the community and constitutes the main source of Soviet power" (Benet, 1970:280).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, a political agent controlled food repositories (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, a political agent controlled food repositories (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The village is well supplied with water, however, as there are many wells in the streets and in the yards of the villagers. An artesian well was drilled in 1955 and water pipes were laid" (Benet, 1970:219).

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The development of railroads changed the flow of bulk merchandise" (Benet, 1970:30).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that taxes were levied only by the village soviet: "It [the village soviet] decides such issues as the type and amount of taxes, electoral procedures, welfare policies, and general methods of improving living conditions in the village" (Benet, 1970:280).

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "It [the village soviet] decides such issues as the type and amount of taxes, electoral procedures, welfare policies, and general methods of improving living conditions in the village" (Benet, 1970:280).

Enforcement

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 90, Police, Russians have a specialized police force (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Because Viriatino interacted with an institutionalized police system that was separate from the religion, it can be assumed that a formal legal code was also present. See SCCS Variable 90, Police (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Warfare

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "These local army groups (composed of local population and demobilized Red Army units) were under the personal military responsibility of a Soviet commandant, and only in areas where it was certain that the villagers were pro-Soviet" (Benet, 1970:173).

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "These local army groups (composed of local population and demobilized Red Army units) were under the personal military responsibility of a Soviet commandant, and only in areas where it was certain that the villagers were pro-Soviet" (Benet, 1970:173).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The focal place of this entry (Viriatino) utilized the Russian language in both religious and non-religious contexts (Shimkin and Adem, 2021).

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The focal place of this entry (Viriatino) utilized the Russian language in both religious and non-religious contexts (Shimkin and Adem, 2021).

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The focal place of this entry (Viriatino) utilized the Russian language in both religious and non-religious contexts (Shimkin and Adem, 2021).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: "The regular nine-, 20- and 40-day memorial cycle [following burial of the deceased] is still observed in Viriatino, but the memorial cycle tied to the church calendar has almost gone out of use, apparently due to the closing of the village church" (Dunn and Dunn, 1988:103).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Russians of Viriatino depend primarily on intensive agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation), with pastoralism (SCCS Variable 206, Dependence on Animal Husbandry) as a secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Pastoralism

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Russians of Viriatino depend primarily on intensive agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation), with pastoralism (SCCS Variable 206, Dependence on Animal Husbandry) as a secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Russians of Viriatino also contributed to a collective farm: "This fundamental reorganization was closely connected to the change from a traditional peasant farm economy to a collective one" (Benet, 1970:245).

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Pastoralism

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Russians of Viriatino depend primarily on intensive agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation), with pastoralism (SCCS Variable 206, Dependence on Animal Husbandry) as a secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).